

Email Lifecycle in an Organizational Context

Afaf Oumy

Department of Information Studies
University of Ottawa
Ottawa, Ontario, Canada

Email: aoumy076@uottawa.ca

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Introduction

In the fast-paced environment of organizational communication, email serves as a pivotal foundation for information exchange. In every organization, there are two types of information: structured information (data) and unstructured information (content) (Baan, 2013). Since most of the information within an organization is unstructured and immense in volume (van der Lans, 2013), it poses a challenge for employees to manage it accurately. According to Albert and Vellino (2016), “the onus of corporate responsibility for managing e-mails lies with all employees, staff still lack both the practical tools and the comprehensive strategies with which to identify which records they must retain.” (p. 294) Organizing information with proper guidelines and appropriate systems in place can enable employees to contribute positively to promoting efficient communication and preserving valuable data. According to the Library and Archives Canada (2014) guidelines on E-mail management, E-mail lifecycle encapsulates seven steps: Planning, Creation, Organization, Use & Dissemination, Protection, Preservation & Disposition, and Evaluation. This framework navigates email lifecycles, encompassing essential aspects like security, compliance, and efficiency. This paper explores Email Lifecycle complexities in organizational settings, going into each stage's processes, identifying challenges and opportunities, and proposing optimizations for enhanced email management.

Phase 1: Planning

One of the organization's modes of communication is through Emails. The amount of information received daily can be overwhelming to maintain. The need to establish proper goals and guidelines will determine the organization's overall performance. There is a risk of data loss (employees accidentally deleting communication threads), productivity loss (the struggle to find

necessary information), and financial consequences (IT costs of storage), which can impact an organization's efficiency. Therefore, the goal of planning is to “ensure that the right information is stored in the right place, at the right time, and for an appropriate length of time.” (LAC, 2014, p. 10) Library and Archives Canada (2014) proposes several aspects to control the flow of Email information in the planning stage. As information professionals, an overall assessment of the organization's habits in dealing with Emails must first be conducted. The following questions can be asked that are aligned with LAC’s proposed steps and serve as action plans:

1. What specific business goals and requirements should the email management policies address? Does the organization deal with sensitive external information (users) or just internal information (organization internal affairs)?
2. What are the current challenges and pain points in our email management practices? How can we prioritize and address challenges related to messages, attachments, and metadata?
3. Can we invest in or upgrade email management software that supports the automation of email content? Will investing in new software also solve storage issues?
4. What governance structures are needed for overall information management? Who will be responsible for the follow-up?
5. How frequently will training sessions be conducted for employees, and how will their effectiveness be measured?

These questions will answer the most critical aspects to be considered in the planning stage of the Email lifecycle for effective management.

Phase 2: Creation and Collection

After setting the plan with predefined rules, the second phase focuses on methods for creating and collecting email information, stressing the importance of accurate data capture.

Popular email services like Outlook, Gmail, and Yahoo offer user-friendly features for document sharing, collaboration, scheduling, calendaring, and task management. E-mails are vehicles for successful knowledge creation (Lichtenstein, 2004), the knowledge extracted from E-mails is critical in defining the following steps to be taken for the recipient. The outcome of the communication between the sender and the recipient should be well-structured to ensure tasks are carried out effectively and will not result in time wasted by the parties involved. According to Albert and Vellino (2016), “in the absence of any corporate guidance, employees’ decision to retain or dispose of e-mail depended mostly on their personal information behaviour habits.” (p. 295) In essence, the lack of training result in employees going by what employees think is right can cause complications, however, certain practices should be established since the beginning when E-mails are created. Using descriptive subject lines can be an example. It lets the recipient know what the email is about before opening it. Assigning priority on importance levels is also a feature in MS Outlook to communicate urgency (Gmail lacks this feature). There are also the Cc and Bcc functions. Employees should learn to distinguish between To, Cc, and Bcc. Most are unaware of the actions and tend to use them randomly. Avoiding the use of the “Reply All” function is also a good practice. It is necessary to assess if the communication can be carried out without involving all parties in the chain. Overall, it is dependent on the organization to offer training on the best practices and assess employees’ compliance along the way.

Phase 3: Organization

Keeping E-mail flow under control can be a real struggle for knowledge workers dealing with what is often called information overload, email overload, communication overload (Kalman & Ravid, 2015, p. 2541) Moreover, effectively managing this struggle will not only ensure tasks are completed within a reasonable time frame, but also make employees feel a sense of

accomplishment. Therefore, in Library and Archives Canada's (2014) guidelines on Email management, there is a list of missions where an information professional should intervene. First, keeping an orderly and effective filing system for managing emails, it is stated that "Email messages, other than non-records or transitory messages, should be moved from the email system to a separate filing system where they should be organized as specified in the classification structure approved by the institution" (LAC, 2014, p. 34) These filing systems can be organized chronologically, alphabetically, project-based, and so on. Project-based filing can be an effective way to manage emails, as it can include all communication related to every project available with its necessary metadata. The latter is what determines the successful retrieval of an information in the filtering process, Treasury Board of Canada (2017) in compliance with metadata model by ISO 23081, suggests the most significant metadata fields to identify an author of an information of business value- Agent Identifier; Agent Name; Agent Role; Agent Corporate Name; and Agent Section Name. For project-based filing systems in large organizations, the metadata proposed by the Treasury Board is beneficial in identifying the various stakeholders involved in the project. Aligning with the organization's needs is crucial when implementing a filing system. Additionally, various CRM Add-ins, like Salesforce, Jira, Asana, and HubSpot, can link email services (e.g., Outlook) to their platforms, organizing information that can later be used in reports and performance tracking. Assessing organizational needs is essential for efficiently organizing emails, not just for communication but also for successful use and retrieval.

Phase 4: Use & Dissemination

The purpose of exchanging Emails in an organization is to communicate information of value. Based on Library and Archives Canada (2014) guidelines, "Institutions must ensure that the use of email supports performance of work that is consistent with their business goals and

objectives” (p. 39). The strategic use of email should enhance productivity, support business initiatives, and ensure accountability. Using E-mails as a communication tool can “help managers be efficient by enabling them to fulfill their managerial function: planning, organizing, leading, and controlling.” (Demirel, 2014, p. 83) Therefore, it is essential to choose an E-mail service that can bind teams together, make them collaborate and share meaning, achievements and goals. Therefore, Emails can replace meetings nowadays, and tagging and ensuring everyone is in the loop is possible with the most popular Email services. There is the possibility to attach documents and files to facilitate information dissemination, enabling collaborators to share reports and presentations. Also, Distribution lists and groups ensure targeted communication, reaching specific audiences without involving unnecessary parties. Threaded conversations maintain context and continuity in discussions, which is beneficial for collaborative projects. Calendar invitations, forwarding options, and notification alerts streamline the scheduling of meetings and provide timely updates. With email archives and search functionality, collaborators can easily retrieve past information. Task assignment, follow-ups, feedback, and discussions are all functions integrated into email communication.

Phase 5: Protection

It is pivotal for an organization to ensure that communication is conducted securely to prevent data breaches. The content in Email exchanges can be critical to an organization, and it must be treated as an asset; therefore, measures to protect and preserve this asset should be given thoughtful consideration. Most popular Email services, such as Outlook and Gmail, use what is called “Transport Layer Security”. The latter is embedded in communication by default, this ensure that emails are secure when in transit, this protocol “aims primarily to provide security, including privacy (confidentiality), integrity, and authenticity through the use of cryptography, such as the

use of certificates, between two or more communicating computer applications” (Wikipedia contributors, 2023, para. 2) However, this protocol is effective only if the recipient email service supports it, i.e., the privacy of the content depends on the encryption the receiving server uses (Bone, 2023, para. 5). There are features to manually secure the content of your email, which is to send in “confidential mode”, however, “confidential mode isn’t secure. While it allows you to set an expiration date for an email and to restrict options to forward, copy, print, or download it, anyone can easily screenshot the message.” (Bone, 2023, para. 24). Therefore, it is necessary to use a service, or an extension of a service, to ensure that communication cannot be accessed and used by third parties. The most reputable encrypted email provider nowadays is ProtonMail. It can be integrated into Outlook and Gmail (if the organization is already using these services and has a hard time switching to a new one) and encrypt and decrypt emails as they enter and leave computers. Protecting data is not only relevant to outside communication, in the planning phase of the Email lifecycle, there should be a clear identification of sensitivity levels of content—identifying what is highly sensitive, moderately so, and what is not. The focus should also be on determining which individuals are granted access to information and making decisions about whether to retain, archive, or delete such data.

Phase 6: Preservation & Disposition

As stated by Library and Archives Canada (2014), content of communication should be preserved in specific and scheduled retention periods, “the key being that the content of the record is what determines how long it should be kept – not the technology or medium used to create it.” (p. 42) To Albert and Vellino (2016), what determines if the content of the email is of business value is the “need to keep track of major project steps for accountability purposes, until a contract is completed.” (p. 300) Within this framework, the value of the content is limited to the duration

of the project. For the National Archives and Records Administration, the retention policy for government records is at least one year (NARA, 2010). Illinois Data Bank data retention policy is a minimum of 5 years (University of Illinois Board of Trustees, 2019). For the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA), “SharePoint Electronic Document and Records Management System (EDRMS), the retention period will be set at the Site or Project level” (CMA, 2022, para.3) and ranges from two years to permanent. From these examples, we can conclude that there are different versions of what is of value to be preserved. Email content, as a record itself, should be assessed based on the organization’s definition of important information. It is essential for institutions to carefully consider their specific needs and legal requirements when determining email preservation and disposition periods. In essence, the nature of the content within the emails, whether they include vital records or sensitive information, can influence retention policies.

Phase 7: Evaluation

For Library and Archives Canada (2014), E-mail management guidelines, the evaluation phase stands as the last phase in the E-mail lifecycle management. This phase is to assess the effectiveness of the process. Once the plan and execution are complete, we can have a holistic view of whether the lifecycle is following best practices. Buchanan and Gibb (2007), in their paper on “The information audit: Role and scope”, propose steps that an organization can follow to ensure a strategic Information Audit. In the context of Email management, these steps should be compared with the desired outcomes specified in the planning phase:

- **Mission:** Was the mission clearly defined? Was it communicated to stakeholders?
- **Goals:** Did the organization achieve its purpose regarding the control of Email flow? Does communication follow the pre-established guidelines? Do employees feel in control of their tasks? Or are they still overwhelmed?

- **Objectives:** Were the targets realized for each step of the lifecycle realistic? Is there evident progress? Are employees compliant with Email policies?
- **Critical Success Factors (CSFs):** Are success factors measurable? Is there an achievement of email-related objectives, such as ensuring secure communication and timely responses?
- **Task/Activity:** Is action taken to ensure CSFs are met?
- **Information Resources:** Are the resources provided to support the achievements of tasks and activities successful? Are the tools provided working well and following the communication protocol and security measures?

The evaluation phase in the email lifecycle involves assessing and analyzing the performance and effectiveness of email-related processes. This includes measuring the success of email communication, evaluating the efficiency of email management tools, and ensuring compliance with organizational policies.

Conclusion

The management of the Email lifecycle is crucial to ensure a healthy workplace where employees are not consumed with tasks that will hinder their productivity. Therefore, Information Professionals should contribute significantly to providing support and help organizations leverage their information assets to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of email management from start to finish. Moreover, to ensure there is added value, information professionals need to understand the organization's structure first, then devise effective strategies and recommendations through each step of the lifecycle. This report has provided a comprehensive examination of the Email Lifecycle within an organizational context, drawing on the Email management guidelines of Library and Archives Canada. This analysis serves as a tentative guide for organizations aiming

to enhance their Email Lifecycle management, while ensuring efficiency, security, and compliance throughout the entire lifecycle.

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